

South Australian AusLAMP Magnetotelluric (MT) Survey Stakeholder Engagement

*A report on the stakeholder engagement and factors contributing to engagement
success*

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INTRODUCTION: THE AUSLAMP PROJECT

In August 2014 the University of Adelaide commenced the South Australian (SA) phase of the national Australian Lithospheric Architecture Magnetotelluric Project (AusLAMP).

AusLAMP is aimed at acquiring magnetotelluric (MT) data across Australia on a grid of approximately 50 x 50 km. These MT measurements can be used to image the electrical resistivity properties of the crust and upper mantle to depths of hundreds of kilometres. Electrical resistivity imaging allows characterisation of the deep-crust and upper mantle, and can define the fundamental building blocks of the lithosphere, as well as delineate major structures and boundaries. This information is of significance to researchers attempting to reconstruct the tectonic evolution of the Australian continent, and also provides fundamental clues about large scale structures which may control mineral deposition and hydrocarbon formation.

AusLAMP is a national collaboration led by Geoscience Australia (GA) with contributions from AuScope (a component of NCRIS, the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy), Australian Universities, research organisations and State and Territory geological surveys. The acquisition phase of AusLAMP will collect over 2800 MT measurements across Australia over the next decade. Figure 1 shows the proposed locations of the AusLAMP stations. The University of Adelaide is Australia's leading university in Magnetotelluric (MT) acquisition, processing and modelling and is the custodian of the AuScope National MT Facility.

Figure 1: Map of Australia showing the distribution of AusLAMP stations at 0.5 degree interval (~55 km). (Source Geoscience Australia AusGeo news)

Preliminary AusLAMP field acquisition commenced in the Flinders Ranges area of South Australia in 2013 by PhD candidate Kate Robinson. This was followed by AusLAMP data acquisition across Victoria, led by GA. Field acquisition in Victoria was completed in mid-2014. From August 2014 to December 2015 the University of Adelaide, with support from GA and the South Australian Department for State Development (DSD), completed a series of three stages in South Australia that covered the southern two-thirds of the State bounded by the Western Australian border to the west, south of an east-west line passing through Coober Pedy to the north, and extended 50 km into NSW in the east (Figure 2). At each survey site an AuScope MT long-period instrument was left to record electric and magnetic field data for a three-week period. A description of the instrumentation and deployment method can be found in Appendix 3. Up to twenty-five instruments were deployed at a time during each individual field trip. The instruments were then recovered and redeployed across the next area of the grid as a moving array.

Figure 2: Map of South Australia showing distribution of survey sites completed to December 2015, and stages of AusLAMP.

Whilst not yet complete, the AusLAMP survey in South Australia has acquired a contiguous long period MT dataset over the largest area achieved anywhere in the world.

The AusLAMP Project in South Australia as of December 2015 was delivered in 3 stages (Figure 2), named here for reporting purposes AusLAMP I, which commenced field activities in September 2014,

AusLAMP East, which commenced field activities in April 2015, and AusLAMP Far West, which commenced field activities in September 2015.

The AusLAMP stages in South Australia have been conducted over a diverse and complex suite of land tenure and land interests including 42 pastoral leases and 40 freehold properties in SA, 9 properties in NSW, 6 national parks and reserves in SA – most co-managed with the traditional Aboriginal peoples, the Maralinga Tjarutja Aboriginal Lands, as well as Woomera Protected Area land managed by the Federal Department of Defence.

The AusLAMP I stage area incorporated pastoral leases and reserve land to the west of Lake Torrens and south of Coober Pedy (Figure 3). Most of these properties were inside the Woomera Prohibited Area. It also included sites on freehold land on the Eyre Peninsula, Yorke Peninsula, Mid North, Adelaide Hills, Fleurieu Peninsular, Mallee and the South East of the State.

AusLAMP East built on MT research data previously acquired previously by the University of Adelaide in AusLAMP 1 and preliminary AusLAMP data from the Flinders Ranges. The campaign incorporated pastoral leases adjacent to the Flinders and Gammon Ranges, and extended 50 km across the border into NSW. One site was also installed on Arkaroola Wilderness Sanctuary. The survey area extended to the Riverland of South Australia which incorporated freehold and reserve land. Sites on Kangaroo Island and in the Mid North were also completed to provide a data set that was contiguous with AusLAMP I data (Figure 3).

AusLAMP Far West comprised a large portion of the western part of SA, and included the Maralinga Tjarutja Aboriginal Lands, Mamungari Conservation Park (CP), Nullarbor Regional Reserve (RR), Nullarbor National Park (NP) and Yellabinna Regional Reserve (RR).

This staged approach was primarily driven by the availability of resources. Factors such as the number of sites in each campaign area, site accessibility and grouping of land tenures all influenced the average cost per site. These considerations were taken into account when planning each stage and component field trips. Also survey areas for each campaign were targeted to build on previous survey effort, ensuring the MT data set built on and was largely contiguous with previous surveys.

Respectful and responsible stakeholder engagement around access to land is of fundamental importance if the AusLAMP project objectives are to be achieved. For the surveys conducted in South Australia so far, engagement with stakeholders has enabled complete and comprehensive land access, and the experiences for both researchers and landholders have been overwhelmingly positive. This report details the community engagement practices and learnings from the three campaigns of AusLAMP completed in SA to date.

Project Management

The project leader for AusLAMP in South Australia is Professor Graham Heinson. Goren Boren ensured the MT equipment was fully serviceable.

AusLAMP 1 was initially project managed by Dr Stephan Thiele, who subsequently left the project to undertake a role within DSD, but continued to provide advice, support and data processing services throughout subsequent campaigns. The project field team maintained a core membership throughout the campaign of Philippa Mawby, Geoff Axford and Dr Bruce Goleby. A number of other personnel assisted the core field team on one or more of the field trips as required including Ray deGraff, Denise Conway, Joe Rugari, John Kennedy, Hugh Avey, Oliver Putland, Kate Robertson, Phoebe Mawby, and Ann Goleby. Ian Hopton from DSD also participated on one field trip.

AusLAMP East was project managed by PhD candidate Kate Robertson. Emma Cordon assisted in liaison with landholders and Native title organisations, and initial site inspections with Aboriginal Heritage monitors. The field team consisted of the core group from AusLAMP 1, namely Philippa Mawby, Geoff Axford and Dr Bruce Goleby, as well as Oliver Putland, Ray DeGraff, Phoebe Mawby, Anne Goleby and Isaac Axford. GA provided several staff including Millie Crowe, Claire Orlov and Richard Chopping, each participating in one field trip.

AusLAMP Far West consisted of the core team of Philippa Mawby, Geoff Axford and Dr Bruce Goleby. Ian Hopton and Stephan Thiele from DSD and Matthew Carey from GA also participated in one field trip each.

LEGISLATIVE AND PROCEDURAL DRIVERS OF ENGAGEMENT

As well as direct engagement with landholders to gain permission to access land for establishing sites, engagement with key stakeholders was necessary to comply with various State and Federal legislation. Engagement was also required with a range of other stakeholders to address a number of procedural considerations including engaging with Native Title groups regarding Aboriginal heritage, developing and implementing adequate processes and procedures to ensure ongoing safety of the project team, and working through challenges associated with accessing accurate landholder contact information.

Aboriginal Heritage Act 1998

The Aboriginal Heritage Act 1988 was established for the protection and preservation of Aboriginal sites, objects and remains. The Project team recognised that the process of locating an MT station on the ground and digging several small holes for installing electrodes and magnetometer created the risk that Aboriginal heritage sites might inadvertently be disturbed. To mitigate this risk a list of site locations was forwarded to SA Government Aboriginal Affairs and Reconciliation Division (AARD) in August 2014 for the proposed AusLAMP I sites, and similarly in April 2015 for AusLAMP East sites, to determine if any proposed MT sites were in the vicinity of Aboriginal heritage sites listed in the Register of Aboriginal Sites and Objects (The Register). The response from AARD indicated several sites of specific concern that required relocation. An example of the AARD response is provided in Appendix 1.

A key point to remember in this process, and this is outlined in AARD responses, is that The Register is not comprehensive, and nor does it represent a legally complete set of sites in any area, and it was recommended that project team liaise with each of the Native Title groups within the survey area to further eliminate any possibility of disturbing an Aboriginal site.

Native Title Act 1994 (SA)

Based on legal advice obtained at the start of the project, the activities undertaken by the project did not trigger any provisions of the Native Title (South Australia) Act 1994 (SA). However, native title claimant groups and registered native title bodies-corporate were still the first point of contact for negotiating the participation of Aboriginal Heritage monitors to assist in appropriately locating sites during deployment of MT equipment on pastoral lease land.

Mining Act 1971

As the project was considered research and not exploration, provisions under Section 58A of the Mining Act 1971 did not apply. Notice of entry notifications to Native Title organisations were not required.

National Parks and Wildlife Act 1972

All research carried out in any of the State's protected areas (including geological research and non-invasive activities such as mapping or remote observations) requires a scientific research permit. Permits were obtained for all DEWNR managed National Parks and Reserves where sites were located. Research permits were granted with a range of conditions relating to access and survey activities. Most importantly for this project most of the National Parks and Reserves accessed were Co-managed with Aboriginal traditional owners. Permit conditions for Co-managed Reserves specified that permission was also required from the relevant Co-Management Board or Co-management Advisory committee and that they themselves may apply further special conditions in relation to undertaking local deployment and collection activities.

Figure 3: Map showing AusLAMP sites located in the Woomera Prohibited Area

Woomera Prohibited Area

The Woomera Prohibited Area (WPA) comprises extensive lands north of the Trans Australia Railway line in South Australia (Figure 3). The WPA is a prohibited area under Commonwealth legislation established for controlling lands associated with military weapons testing undertaken at the Woomera Range Complex. The WPA is South Australian Crown Land and is covered by Pastoral leases, reserves, Aboriginal freehold land and mining tenements. Access requires permits, with conditions on the permits dependent on the zone divisions within the WPA. For the Infrequent Use Zone and Periodic a permit was required but access was largely unrestricted, however access to the Periodic Use Zone 2 and the Continuous Use Zone necessitated a Range Liaison Officer to be present during deployment and collection of equipment.

Guidelines for Ethical Research in Australian Indigenous Studies

The following information is taken from The Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies (AIATSIS) website at <http://aiatsis.gov.au/research/ethical-research/guidelines-ethical-research-australian-indigenous-studies>. AIATSIS has created the Guidelines for Ethical Research in Australian Indigenous Studies (GERAIS) to ensure that research with and about Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples follows a process of meaningful engagement and reciprocity between the researcher and the individuals and/or communities involved in the research. See (<http://aiatsis.gov.au/sites/default/files/docs/research-and-guides/ethics/gerais.pdf>).

The latest edition, published in 2012, embodies the best standards of ethical research and human rights. The guidelines have been regularly revised to reflect developments in critical areas that have emerged since previous editions. These include changes to intellectual property laws, rights in traditional knowledge and traditional cultural expressions, and the establishment of agreements and protocols between Indigenous people and researchers as well as emerging developments in digitisation, data and information management, and the very significant impacts this has on research and other aspects of Indigenous studies.

AIATSIS recognises that it has responsibility as a leading institution in Australian Indigenous studies to provide and facilitate ethics guidelines as an essential tool to inform all research in this area.

The GERAIS comprise a set of principles grouped under the following six categories:

- Rights, respect and recognition
- Negotiation, consultation, agreement and mutual understanding
- Participation, collaboration and partnership
- Benefits, outcomes and giving back
- Managing research: use, storage and access
- Reporting and compliance.

It is the belief of the researchers and field workers on the AusLAMP Project that all attempts were made to follow these principles and we will endeavour to continue to do so as the project continues throughout Australia.

Indigenous Heritage

In July 2014 field team members met with the State Aboriginal Heritage Committee of AARD within DSD. The project objectives and methodology were discussed and advice sought from the Committee on the best way to engage with the Aboriginal community on the implementation of AusLAMP in SA. The key message from this Committee was that there is no single point of contact for working through Aboriginal heritage issues, and that we would have to work separately with each of the Native Title and Aboriginal land holding organisations within the campaign area.

On Aboriginal owned land and state owned reserves that were Co-managed with Aboriginal native title owners, the approach to addressing any Aboriginal Heritage concerns were prescribed by the relevant Council or Board responsible for overseeing the management of the respective land or reserve. This always involved the project team taking Aboriginal people on to Country to inspect proposed site locations before deploying the equipment.

It is important to note that throughout this report the term ‘Heritage Monitor’ is used to describe the Aboriginal people nominated to accompany the field team as opposed to other descriptors such as ‘Traditional Owner’. This is because in many instances the Aboriginal people nominated were not

necessarily traditional owners for the country where the field team were operating, but were authorised by their respective Native Title organisations, Land Holding authority or communities to effectively work with the team to ensure location of sites was culturally appropriate.

For Aboriginal Heritage concerns on *pastoral leases* the approach initially was to follow the minimum legal requirements of the Aboriginal Heritage Act, namely to provide AARD with a list of the site locations and then adjust the location of any site if it were in the vicinity of a registered site. However part way through the AusLAMP 1 campaign this approach was reconsidered, and the project team decided that, in addition to Aboriginal Heritage Act requirements, Heritage Monitors would henceforth be engaged to ensure that all sites on pastoral leases were placed in culturally appropriate locations. This was decided for four reasons. Firstly, to guarantee there were no inadvertent impacts on Aboriginal cultural heritage; secondly to demonstrate appropriate respect to the Native Title Owners; thirdly, to build good working relationships with the Aboriginal community as a foundation for future research work by the University of Adelaide; and finally that project resources were adequate to cover the increased costs associated with employing Heritage Monitors. The project team used a contact list provided by the Aboriginal affairs and Reconciliation division of the Department for State Development to contact the relevant Aboriginal groups/organisations.

For Aboriginal heritage concerns on freehold land the approach was to follow the minimum legal requirements of the Aboriginal Heritage Act. The rationale for this was that sites on freehold land were located within highly altered landscapes - mostly cleared and often cultivated land where there was no likelihood of impact on Aboriginal heritage resulting from project activities.

Occupational Health and Safety

Throughout each of the AusLAMP campaigns the field team were regularly required to drive long distances on unformed roads and operate in extremely remote locations far from mobile phone networks and emergency support services. Ensuring the safety of the field team was of paramount importance. The field team undertook training in safe handling of 4wd and remote area first aid. Prior to each filed trip a significant amount of effort was dedicated to undertake and document plans, risk assessments, scheduled call-in procedures and emergency response procedures to ensure the safety of the field team. This necessitated engaging with a wide range of stakeholders – particularly for coordinating the various scheduled call-in procedures for the different organisations contributing personnel to the field team, including the University of Adelaide, Geosciences Australia, SA Department of State Development and OPM Consulting.

Determining site locations

Determining site locations for installing MT equipment was an iterative process. The starting point for locating each site was the confluence of every half degree of latitude and longitude (the approximate 55 x 55 km grid). Sites were then adjusted to locations adjacent to the closest roads, tracks or fence lines as close to the confluence point as possible using topographic maps and google earth. Site locations were then further adjusted if there were any registered heritage sites located nearby based on information received from AARD. In the field prior to deployment site locations were then refined further after consideration of any landholder concerns or advice and if necessary adjustments were made to accommodate any issues identified by Heritage Monitors.

Figure 4: Native Title Application and Determination areas within the AusLAMP Survey Area.

Accessing Land Owner Contact Information

In both SA and NSW, acquisition of accurate and current land ownership information from respective state authorities is not trivial, and so the process of acquiring accurate contact information for current land owners was complicated and time-consuming. Each type of land tenure required a different approach.

Lessee contact information for pastoral leases in SA was obtained through the DEWNR Pastoral Management Unit. This information was reasonably comprehensive, though further refinement was required using the existing knowledge and networks of members of the project team.

Accessing the contact details for freehold landowners in SA was considerably more difficult. The DSD was able to provide the project team with a somewhat dated cadastral layer which provided the parcel number and name of landowners where potential sites were located. The names of the land parcel owners were then matched to listings in the district of the same name using Yellow Pages search on the internet. As the cadastre information was several years old some parcels of land had changed ownership. However, most people contacted through yellow pages searches who were not current owners of the land were willing to provide contact details of actual owners or at least suggest how the current owners might be contacted.

Similarly, in NSW project team staff were able to access cadastre data from networks within the NSW government which provided the land owner name for each land parcel within the survey area. These names were then matched to listings in the district of the same name using yellow pages search on the internet. Again the cadastre information was 10 years old and so a significant number of properties had changes hands.

Contact information for DEWNR managed reserves was acquired through the DEWNR website, specifically via the DEWNR Research Permit Unit. Likewise, contact details for the Maralinga Tjarutja Incorporated and the Woomera Prohibited Area were obtained from their respective websites.

Figure 5: Pastoral leases within the AusLAMP 1 and AusLAMP East survey areas

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT - AUSLAMP I

Planning and landholder engagement for AusLAMP I commenced in August 2014. The campaign consisted of 12 field trips, with the first 4 field trips focussed on deploying MT stations on pastoral leases between Port Augusta and William Creek (Figure 5), gradually moving westwards to include pastoral properties north of Tarcoola and south and west of Coober Pedy, including the Tallaringa Conservation Park. The field trips during January and February of 2015 incorporated deployment on freehold properties of the Fleurieu Peninsula, Adelaide Hills, Murray Mallee and South East SA. In March to May 2015 the final trips of the campaign deployed sites on pastoral leases in the Gawler Ranges area north-west of Port Augusta and the eastern portion of the Yellabinna Regional Reserve north of Ceduna, followed by small infill work on Eyre and Yorke Peninsulas.

Engagement of Pastoral Lessees and freehold land owners

Contacting pastoral leases and freehold landholders was staged to allow landholders the time to consider the proposal, ask questions and build trust with project staff. Generally first contact with landholders was by telephone approximately 5 weeks prior to planned deployment on their property. A number of important points were emphasised during this first conversation including that:

- the University of Adelaide was conducting the research;
- the activities were research - not exploration or mining;
- the potential site locations and timing of installation could be modified to suit the landholders concerns, i.e. they retained control ,
- the equipment is passive and does not emit any chemical or electromagnetic radiation – the equipment would not compromise products produced on their property.

Many landholders gave verbal permission during this first conversation. A follow-up email (Appendix 2) was sent immediately following the initial phone call containing additional information including a project information sheet (Appendix 3) and maps of each proposed site on their property (Appendix 4). The third contact by follow-up phone call was undertaken several days after the email, confirming or seeking final permission to access their land and confirming the proposed date of deployment. For pastoral leases permission to access a detailed paddock plan of their property from the DEWNR Pastoral Management Unit was sought in this conversation. A final email was then sent to the landholder confirming arrangements and thanking them for their involvement.

Landholders were contacted by telephone approximately 1-2 days prior to arrival on their property as a courtesy to remind them of the imminent deployment and fine tune any arrangements to meet face to face. Face to face meetings mostly occurred at the homestead or at a location on the property convenient to the landholder. At these meetings the site locations, site accessibility and property management issues were discussed and any site locality adjustments negotiated. Once this conversation was completed most landholders continued with their own work and allowed the deployment team to undertake the installation unaccompanied. Following installation of the equipment the deployment team would contact the landholder on departure from the property or call the landholder that evening to reassure them that the team had left the property safely, reiterate that the team would be back in 3 weeks, and thank them again for their involvement.

For collection of equipment a reminder phone call was made to the landholder 1-2 days prior to arrival at the property. Any access, timing or other issues were discussed at this time. As with deployment, final contact was made wherever possible with the landholder soon after departure from the property to thank the landholder and as a courtesy to let them know the team had left their property safely.

Figure 6: AusLAMP 1 survey area

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Figure 7: Field team member Geoff Axford discussing site location details with the manager of Stuarts Creek Station Dion Kahn.

A permit to enter the Woomera Protected Area was obtained prior to undertaking the field program. Ongoing contact occurred with the WPA in the lead up to and during deployment activities and a range officer accompanied the field team during deployment and retrieval of sites within the Red Zone on Coondambo Station and Parakylia Station (Figure 4).

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Indigenous Engagement

The first engagement with the Aboriginal community for AusLAMP 1 was in relation to accessing Mabel Creek Station (Figure 3) which is owned by the Antakirinja Matu-Yankunytjatjara Aboriginal Corporation (AMYAC). Contact was made with the South Australian Native Title Service (SANTS) as the first point of contact for the AMYAC for access to Mabel Creek Station. In addition, Tallaringa Conservation Park (Figure 3) is co-managed by DEWNR and AMYAC. A research permit for Tallaringa CP was obtained from DEWNR and per conditions specified in the permit, contact was made with the District Council of Coober Pedy who provide executive support to the Tallaringa Conservation Park Co-Management Advisory Committee, asking them to consider the request for MT research to be conducted in the Tallaringa CP. The advisory committee considered the request and set an additional condition that Aboriginal Heritage Monitors should be present when locating sites in the Park. Conveniently AMYAC, as the body corporate representing the traditional owners of the park and owners of Mabel Creek station, nominated Mr Barney Lennon of Coober Pedy and Mr Joe Lennon Jnr also of Coober Pedy to assist the project team in both places. Their contact details were provided by SANTS to the field team who were then able liaise directly with Barney and Joe to prepare for the field trip. Prior to heading out to Mabel Creek and Tallaringa CP during field trip 3, Barney and Joe were collected from their homes in Coober Pedy and over the following two days sites on Tallaringa CP and Mabel Creek Station were located and installed. Two vehicles were used to carry personnel, camp gear and MT equipment. The field team camped out on Tallaringa CP. The Heritage Monitors had no concerns with any of the tentative site locations. The field team organised to have Barney and Joe participate in the collection of the equipment 3 weeks later however they were unable to attend at the last minute because of a funeral, but were happy for the project team to collect the boxes without them.

Similarly, the scientific research permit conditions for Yellabinna RR specified that the project team liaise with the Far West Coast Native Title Corporation in relation to deployment activities on Yellabinna RR. The Far West Native Title Corporation nominated Sue Haseldine, Wayne Haseldine and Dorcas Miller. Deployment in the eastern portion of Yellabinna RR occurred during field trip 6. An R44 Helicopter was used to locate and install sites as there are minimal access roads and tracks in Yellabinna RR. As the sites were within relative close proximity to Ceduna the helicopter was able to undertake sorties to deploy sites and return to its base in Ceduna in the evening. Support vehicles were positioned at Googes Lake and other locations to provide fuel and MT equipment and supplies for the helicopter operations. Deploying the site on the first flight was not possible as the helicopter was too small to carry traditional owners, MT equipment and a technician. Consequently Sue, Wayne and a project team member were flown to each site to ensure the locations were appropriate. On a second flight the sites were installed by a field team technician. Dorcas was not comfortable with flying in a helicopter but was able to drive to those sites within her country.

The final pastoral area to be deployed in the AusLAMP 1 campaign was the Gawler Ranges for field trip 6. This was to be the first time heritage monitors were to accompany the field team for all sites on pastoral leases after the project reconsidered its approach to Aboriginal heritage on pastoral lease land. In early November a request was made to the Gawler Ranges Native Title Corporation through SANTS for them to nominate two traditional owners to assist the project team in ensuring sites on pastoral leases were positioned in culturally appropriate locations. Brandon MacNamara and Kenny Smith were nominated by the Gawler Ranges Native Title Corporation, and SANTS provided the field team with their contact details so that the field team could liaise directly with Brandon and Kenny to make arrangements for the field deployment. Kenny and Brandon accompanied the project team over a 3 day period during field trip 6. Commencing at Pt Augusta where Brandon and Kenny were collected, the field team worked their way west through the Gawler Ranges sites, staying at Mt Ive Station on the first night and camping in swags on Lake Everard Station on the second night, returning to Pt

Augusta on the final night. Branden and Kenny actively participated in the installation of equipment. At the end of the field trip they were very complementary of the way the field team looked after them, and of the way the field team respected their views and input.

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STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT - AUSLAMP EAST

The AusLAMP East campaign consisted of a series of 5 field trips commencing in June 2015. The aim of the AusLAMP East campaign was to infill areas between AusLAMP 1 and sites previously installed in the Flinders and Gammon Ranges by PhD student Kate Robertson, and to extend coverage of sites into NSW (Figure 8). In addition infill sites were installed on Kangaroo Island. The 5 trips including:

Field Trip 1: Deployment on pastoral leases to the west, north and east of the Flinders Ranges, including Arkaroola Wilderness Sanctuary and deployment on properties in the Broken Hill area.

Field Trip 2: Collection of sites on pastoral leases to the west, north and east of the Flinders Ranges, including Arkaroola Wilderness Sanctuary and deployment on properties in the Broken Hill area and deploying sites north and west of Broken Hill.

Field Trip 3: Collection of sites north, west and south of Broken Hill and deployment of sites south of Broken Hill and the Riverland area of SA.

Field Trip 4: Collection of sites South of Broken Hill and Riverland area and deployment of sites on Kangaroo Island

Field Trip 5: Collection of sites on Kangaroo Island

Engagement with Pastoral Lessees and freehold land owners

The process used to engage with pastoral lessees within South Australia for AusLAMP East was the same approach employed in AusLAMP 1. However for properties in NSW the time between initial contact with the landholder and planned deployment was much shorter. In several cases the relevant information was obtained only a week prior to the scheduled field deployment trip. To compound matters the initial plan for field trip 2 was to install sites on properties north of the Barrier Highway on the SA side of the NSW border, however rainfall in this area during the second field trip necessitated moving deployment activities to the Broken Hill area where safe access to sites was not compromised by the rain. Because of the sudden program change no previous engagement work had been undertaken with the property owners in the Broken Hill area. Understandably several landholders contacted were initially not particularly happy with the short notice, but all gave permission to deploy equipment. More of a problem was that a number of landholders were un-contactable as they were away from the homestead when contacted by phone. Due to the immediate need to access sites alternative landholders in the vicinity were contacted to find a landholder who was willing to have a site deployed on their property at short notice.

During field trip 1 and 2 a significant amount of rainfall occurred in the area which resulted in delays and alterations to deployment routes. Landholders were very accommodating considering the wet conditions. In particular Mt Lyndhurst Station (Figure 5) generously made their shearers quarters available, where the field team were able to refuge for several days whilst it was too wet to use roads, let alone to deploy equipment.

Interestingly, the 1:250,000 topographic maps for western NSW used very old and inaccurate information compared to coverages in South Australia. Obtaining clear instructions from the landholders on how to access proposed site locations was critical in obtaining information on how to access sites using station tracks.

Indigenous Engagement

The distribution of sites on pastoral leases surrounding the Flinders and Gammon Ranges and the sites east of Lake Frome extending into NSW incorporated the traditional lands of the Adnyamathanha, Dieri, Malyangapa, Wilykalyi and Barkanji people (Figure 4). The involvement of so many native title groups made the process of organising Heritage Monitors for inspecting sites complex indeed. Contact was made by telephone and email to the legal organisations representing the Adnyamathanha Traditional Lands Association (ATLA), the Dieri Aboriginal Corporation requesting the nomination of traditional owners to assist the project team. Contact was also made with the legal representatives of the Malyangapa people who at the time of this survey did not have a body corporate. Initially each group provided the names of two traditional owners to participate in the program, however at the time of undertaking site inspections only one traditional owner from each of the groups was available.

Figure 8: AusLAMP East Survey Area

To expedite the process of inspecting proposed sites the project team utilised a helicopter to fly all the proposed sites on the Adnyamathanha, Dieri and Malyangapa sites in SA. On June 3 2015 the project team, helicopter pilot, support crew and Mr Cliff Coulthard (Adnyamathanha traditional owner) and Mr Gerald Quale (Malyangapa traditional owner) rendezvoused at Yunta on the Barrier Highway. Cliff and Gerald together with a project team member inspected each of the site locations on their respective country. Malyangapa country was flown first and on completion of the Malyangapa sites Gerald disembarked from the helicopter and drove home to Broken Hill, while Cliff and 2 project team

members continued to inspect sites on Adnyamathanha country west of the Flinders and Gammon Ranges. The helicopter pilot, project team and chopper support crew stayed at Arkaroola overnight and continued on to Marree the following morning inspecting Adnyamathanha sites north of the Gammon ranges along the way. Cliff disembarked from the helicopter at Marree and Jeffrey Naylor (Dieri traditional owner) flew with a project team member to inspect sites on Dieri lands in the vicinity of Marree and east of Marree into the Strzelecki Desert. The helicopter then returned to Marree where Jeffrey Naylor disembarked the helicopter and then Cliff continued in the helicopter inspecting proposed sites on pastoral leases in Adnyamathanha country adjacent to Lake Torrens on the western side of the Flinders and Gammon Ranges, ending the flight at Hawker Airstrip. Cliff returned to Port Augusta by vehicle and the project team returned to Adelaide. All site locations were approved by the various Heritage Monitors without any need for relocation. Using a helicopter allowed all sites to be inspected by Heritage Monitors prior to deployment. This allowed the field team much greater flexibility and reducing planning, driving, logistics and catering on the deployment field trips. This proved to be particularly important following the significant and sudden changes to the deployment program in response to rainfall that restricted access to many sites during trips 1 and 2.

For deployment in NSW the Aboriginal heritage inspection was undertaken at same time as deployment, using vehicle to access all sites. For sites on pastoral properties north of Broken Hill in Malyangapa country, Gerald Quale accompanied the project team. For Barkandji country around Broken Hill and south of Broken Hill, contact was made with the Broken Hill Local Aboriginal Land Council and Raymond O'Donnell (a Barkandji traditional owner) was nominated to accompany the project team during field deployment. Both Gerald and Raymond not only provided advice regarding the cultural heritage appropriateness of the site locations, but also showed real interest in the project objectives and provided enthusiastic and valuable assistance in installing the MT equipment.

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STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT - FAR WEST

The engagement process for gaining access to the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands, Mamungari Conservation Park (CP) and the reserves of the Far West Coast (Figure 10) was considerably different to the previous campaigns of the AusLAMP project. This remote area in the western part of South Australia has no pastoral or freehold land, but is either Aboriginal Conditional Freehold or State-owned Reserve land managed collaboratively with the DEWNR and Aboriginal traditional owners. The area is vast and the Aboriginal people from this area include the Maralinga, Ngalia, Mirning, Pila Nguru and Kokotha, and collectively refer to themselves as Anangu. There are 4 main, widely dispersed communities in the far west where many people with traditional ties to the survey area live, namely Ceduna, Yalata and Oak Valley in SA, and Tjuntjuntjara in WA. Initial contact with the various land holding and land management entities in the Far West occurred in September 2014 –many months ahead of scheduled field deployment in this area. Engaging early was a deliberate strategy by the project team to provide sufficient lead time as the process for considering the request can be prolonged and involved iterations of meetings and discussions. The engagement process for each land holding or land management entity is detailed below.

Figure 10: AusLAMP Far West Survey area and the location of the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands, Mamungari CP, Oak Valley Community, Nullarbor National Park, Nullarbor Regional Reserve, and Yellabinna Regional Reserve.

Access by vehicle in many parts of these lands was limited as there were relatively few tracks and roads, so the use of a helicopter was necessary to undertake deployment and collection of MT equipment at inaccessible sites. Often the entire project team, helicopter pilot and support vehicle and Heritage Monitors were camped out in remote locations for a number of days, which required careful

planning around logistics, flight path planning and coordination, safety, meals and camp support. To add further complexity to the process this work was undertaken in a truly cross cultural context.

Initial Engagement - Maralinga Tjarutja Council

Initial contact with Maralinga Tjarutja Council occurred in September 2014 by telephone with the General Manager, approximately 7 months prior to the scheduled date for deployment on the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands. This was followed by a detailed email requesting formal permission from the Maralinga Tjarutja Council to access the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands for survey activities. A face to face meeting occurred with the General Manager in the Maralinga Tjarutja Council office in Ceduna to discuss the proposal in late September 2015. Over the ensuing months contact by phone and email was maintained with the Maralinga Tjarutja office. However by February 2015 the Maralinga Tjarutja Council had not considered the request.

In early 2015 a new General Manager was appointed and in February 2015 project team staff met with the new General Manager to discuss the proposal. Following this meeting the request was included in the next Maralinga Tjarutja Council meeting and project team staff were invited to present to the Council at their meeting in Oak Valley in April 2015. Project team representatives attended the meeting where the equipment was demonstrated and discussions regarding timing, approach and purpose of the project were held with the Council. The Maralinga Tjarutja Council emphasised that employment outcomes were its major priority and permission for the survey to proceed was granted subject to the employment of 4 elders to undertake heritage monitoring during all deployment and collection activities conducted on the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands.

Initial Engagement - Mamungari Conservation Park Co-Management Board

Located in the North West corner of the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands is the Mamungari CP (Figure 10). It is a tier 1 Co Managed Reserve, meaning that it is land owned by the Maralinga Tjarutja people, and leased back to the government for the purpose of conservation and managed co-operatively with traditional owners and the Department of Environment, Water and Natural Resources (DEWNR). Management of the park is overseen by a Co-Management Board consisting of traditional owners and DEWNR representatives. Initial contact to access Mamungari CP occurred formally through the research permit unit of DEWNR as per other DEWNR managed reserves.

University project staff met with a number DEWNR staff from the Alintjara Willurara Natural Resources Management (AWNRM) Region who have operational responsibility for the management of the Reserve to discuss the project prior to attending a Mamungari CP Co-Management Board meeting on the reserve in September 2014. At this meeting project staff demonstrated the equipment and discussed the purpose and objective of the project. The Board remained undecided and requested to meet with the project manager at their next meeting in December in Adelaide. Professor Graham Heinson attended this meeting, and subsequently permission for the project to proceed on Mamungari CP was gained from the Board.

Initial Engagement - Reserves of the Far West Coast

The reserves of the Far West Coast include the Nullarbor Regional Reserve, the Yellabinna Regional Reserve and the Nullarbor National Park (Figure 5). The management of these reserves is shared between DEWNR and the Far West Coast Native Title Group under a co-management arrangement. The research permit obtained for each of these reserves specified that access to these reserves would be subject to conditions set by the Far West Coast Aboriginal Corporation. Phone and email communications were initiated in September 2014. Approval for access was granted with the condition that Heritage Monitors be in attendance when locating sites. Ten sites were deployed as part of the AusLAMP I campaign on the eastern part of the Yellabinna Regional Reserve in March 2015. The

remainder of sites on the reserves of the Far West Coast were deployed in between October and December 2015.

First Deployment Trip: 14-23 September 2015

The first field trip focussed on deploying MT equipment on sites that were located entirely on the eastern side of the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands. This was a deliberate strategy to ensure the collection of a largely contiguous data set from the work undertaken in the AusLAMP I campaign, and to simplify engagement with Traditional Owners and associated logistics. Subsequent field trips incorporated site collection and deployment on Maralinga Tjarutja land, Mamungari CP and Far West Coast reserves concurrently, with each requiring the presence of different heritage monitors. This created considerable organisational challenges for the project team as the deployment program transitioned across the landscape.

The Field Team consisted of Philippa Mawby, Geoff Axford, Dr Bruce Goleby, and Ian Hopton from SA Department of State Development. Also accompanying the team were the helicopter pilot Tim Anderson, and helicopter support provided by Erin Gibson.

The only community located on the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands is Oak Valley, which is over 400 km north-west of Ceduna (Figure 4) and centrally located within the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands. Oak Valley has a small store selling basic food items and fuel. Throughout the work undertaken on the Maralinga Tjarutja lands and Mamungari CP the staff and community members of Oak Valley were always very supportive and helpful. All of the heritage monitors involved in the survey on Maralinga Tjarutja lands were members of the Oak Valley community. For these reasons Oak Valley was an important strategic location for the field deployment team.

In the weeks preceding the initial September deployment a number of attempts were made to obtain the names of community members to accompany the survey team as cultural heritage monitors. Fortunately the Deputy Chair of the Oak Valley Community Council, Mr Roger Williams, was nominated as one of the community members to be accompanying the Field Team. Contact was made by telephone with Roger prior to arrival and he provided a very significant leadership role as the key contact for the project team whilst working on the Maralinga Tjarutja Lands.

On arrival at Oak Valley the project team met with Roger Williams to discuss and refine a deployment plan with the field crew, and to determine which heritage Monitors would be accompanying the field team. This plan involved the ground vehicles travelling around the survey area in an anti-clockwise direction. The vehicle based teams were to deploy sites along the roads and provide support to the helicopter undertaking the remote site deployments. The plan necessitated camping away from the community for several days so the vehicles had to carry provisions for all participants. None of the Heritage Monitors had camping gear and so swags were generously borrowed from the Alinjara Willurara Natural Resource Management (AWNRM) Board's camping equipment stored on site at Oak Valley.

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Four Maralinga-Tjarutja Heritage Monitors, namely Roger Williams, Leon Brown, Thomas Samdimar and Mr Ricky (Marcus) May, travelled with the MT Field Crew. Two monitors travelled in the helicopter during each sortie to give permission to install the MT equipment at sites deployed by helicopter, and to assist in the installation of the MT equipment. The other two monitors travelled with the vehicles to give similar permission to install the MT equipment at sites and to assist in the installation of the MT equipment.

The Heritage Monitors and the MT Field Crew alternated between the vehicle deployment teams and helicopter deployment team.

On completion of the first deployment trip Mr Roger Williams was asked if he and the other monitors were happy with how the trip was undertaken, and invited to give feedback on how future deployment trips could be improved. He indicated that the monitors and broader Oak Valley community were very happy and the field team should run all future deployment trips on Maralinga Tjarutja lands in the same manner.

Second Deployment Trip: October 12-24 2015

The second deployment trip was considerably more complex than the first, requiring collection of sites deployed in the first trip and then redeploying them on Maralinga Tjarutja land, Mamungari CP and on the Nullarbor Regional Reserve.

The Field Team were accompanied again by the helicopter pilot Tim Anderson, and helicopter support was provided by Zoe Anderson.

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To simplify logistics the field team decided to undertake deployment of Mamungari CP first. As a condition of permit, the Mamungari CP Co-Management Board nominated two male and two female Traditional Owners, and they were to be present during all deployment activities on the park. Prior to the survey commencing, a request was received to take an additional female Traditional Owner into the field. This was accepted so the survey had five heritage monitors Bruce Hogan, Tommy Baker, Margaret May, Cindy Watson and Dora Queema. Two sites on the park were identified by the heritage monitors as Women Only sites, so for these sites MT Field Crew member Ms Philippa Mawby accompanied two of the ladies to these areas and deployed these sites. The rest of the Mamungari CP sites had no identified gender issues.

On completion of deployment on Mamungari CP the field team then progressed back onto Maralinga Tjarutja land. Once again, four Maralinga-Tjarutja cultural Heritage Monitors Ricky (Marcus) May, Phillip Williams, Mr Milton Kugena and Roger Williams, travelled with the MT Field Crew. Two Heritage Monitors travelled in the helicopter and the other two travelled with the vehicles to give similar permission to install the MT equipment at the site, to take a soil samples and to assist in the installation of the MT equipment. The Heritage Monitors and the MT Field Crew rotated between the vehicle and helicopter deployment teams.

For deployments in Far West Coast Lands, two Far West Coast Heritage Monitors John Mungee and Aaron Edwards travelled with the MT Field Crew, travelling in the helicopter to all sites to either assist with deployment or clear sites for future deployment.

Third Deployment Trip: November 11-22 2015

The focus of the third deployment trip was to collect equipment at sites deployed on the Maralinga Tjarutaja Lands, Mamungari CP and central Nullarbor and to deploy the last suite of sites on Nullarbor National Park in Mirning country. The field team consisted of Philippa Mawby, Geoff Axford, Dr Bruce Goleby, Matthew Carey from Geoscience Australia, and Ian Hopton from SA Department of State Development. Also accompanying the team were the helicopter pilot Tim Anderson and helicopter support provided by Erin Gibson.

For retrieval of MT equipment on Mamungari CP Tommy Baker, Cindy Watson, and Elaine Cox accompanied the field team. For retrieval of the MT site near an identified Women Only site, MT Field team member Ms Philippa Mawby was accompanied by Ms Cindy Watson to recover this site to ensure cultural sensitivities were respected.

For deployments in Maralinga-Tjarutja Lands, Maralinga-Tjarutja heritage monitors were asked to join the MT Field Crew. As this trip was only retrieving 6 sites, of which only one was accessible by road and there was no space in the helicopter, permission was granted for the MT Survey team to retrieve the sites without heritage monitors being present.

For deployment and retrievals in the Far West Coast Lands, two Far West Coast Elders, Mr John Mungee and Mr Roy Day, who were responsible for the northern Nullarbor, accompanied the MT Field Crew, travelling by vehicle to selected sites to retrieve equipment in the central and northern sections of the Nullarbor. The crew also included a third Far West Coast elder, James Peel, who was responsible for the southern Nullarbor in Mirning country. Once the sites were retrieved all MT Survey Crew and elders proceeded to the southern Nullarbor to deploy 4 sites near the route of the old Eyre Highway across the southern Nullarbor.

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Final Deployment Trip: December 3-10 2015

This field trip retrieved the last 11 sites deployed during Field Trip 3. These included the collection of redeployed sites within the Mamungari CP and the south western corner of the Maralinga-Tjarutja lands, collection of sites deployed in the Nullarbor National Park; and the collection of redeployed sites on the Eyre Peninsula, Gawler Ranges and Central Flinders. All sites were accessed by vehicle.

The field team consisted of Philippa Mawby, Geoff Axford, Dr Bruce Goleby and Ms Phoebe Mawby.

For retrievals in the northern and central Nullarbor area the Far West Coast Native Title Corporation nominated Mr John Mungee and Mr Roy Day to undertake heritage monitoring role with the field team. For the Nullarbor National Park area the Far West Coast Native Title Corporation nominated James Peel and Anton Mundy. Anton Mundy joined the field team at Iron Knob and James, John and Roy all joined the field team at Yalata. Sites in the Nullarbor National Park were collected first, necessitating an overnight camp at Koonalda Caves. The remaining sites were collected the following day and the field team returned to Yalata. At this stage the field team split, with team one, consisting of one vehicle collecting sites on the Eyre Peninsular and then returning to Adelaide. Team two, consisting of two vehicles, made their way to Oak Valley for retrieval of the remaining sites in Mamungari CP and Maralinga-Tjarutja Lands. The newly appointed Chair of the Oak Valley Community Council, Mr Leon Ingomar, nominated Mr Nathaniel Williams and Mr Russell Gibson to participate as Heritage Monitors. Both provided good support in the field work. On completion of the collection of the equipment in these areas team two drove to the Gawler Ranges to collect two redeployed sites then returned to Adelaide.

FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO ENGAGEMENT SUCCESS

From a stakeholder engagement perspective AusLAMP in South Australia has been highly successful. Without exception landholders in the pastoral and freehold areas of the State were accommodating, interested and supportive of project activities undertaken on their land. Access was gained to all identified pastoral leases and Aboriginal owned land and Co-managed reserves. This was particularly important as these landholdings were very large with many of these landholdings having several sites located on them. Anna Creek station for example had 6 sites. Failure to access a property would have potentially resulted in significant gaps in the MT data set. In western NSW where the field team were not able to follow the recommended landholder liaison process, resulted in less optimal interaction with landholders. Nonetheless full site coverage was achieved in this area.

Landholders kept all commitments to maintaining sites free of livestock or other interference to equipment and at no time did survey activities cause any contentious issues or complaints. All Aboriginal Heritage Monitors working with the project team were complimentary of the way in which the project team worked to ensure Aboriginal heritage issues were respected, and were appreciative of the way they were welcomed and looked after in the deployment camp on country.

There are a range of factors identified by the project team that contributed to engagement success. Most were already well understood by the project team at the outset and were incorporated in project planning and delivery. Others factors were adopted by the project team through trial and error during project delivery. The key factors which the field team consider to be most important are discussed below. Particular detail is provided regarding engagement with Aboriginal organisations because access to Aboriginal owned and managed land, and utilisation of Aboriginal Heritage monitors have been a major and essential component of this project.

University research rather than ‘government’ or ‘exploration’ activity

Many landholders, particularly in the more remote parts of the state, are familiar with exploration companies accessing their land. Many landholders are suspicious of exploration activities and often perceived exploration as an impost on their business and country. The Magneto-telluric methodology employed by this survey is similar to other geophysical exploration methodologies such as ground based magnetics and gravity surveys, and so could easily be perceived as ‘exploration’ by landholders. By the project being presented as University of Adelaide research, it was more positively viewed by landholders, who were generally very supportive of their property being part of a research project that builds fundamental knowledge about the nature of the earth’s crust.

Respect, empathy and honesty

Regardless of land tenure and cultural background of stakeholders, the fundamental elements of engagement employed by the project team were to be respectful, empathic and honest in dealings with all stakeholders. This ensured the establishment of trust based relationships with landholders. During all deployment activities the project team were appreciative of being allowed access to the property, always followed land owner instructions and showed an interest in, and empathy for the landowner’s property and business. The project team were always appreciative when land owners took time off their work to meet with the team. When undertaking field deployment the project team were always respectful that they were on someone’s land, regardless if the property were a small hobby farm or on the vast pastoral properties or Aboriginal owned lands, which may seem uninhabited and unmanaged, yet are in effect the ‘back yard’ of a pastoral and/or Aboriginal landowner.

Engage early and appropriately

The engagement process is essentially the establishment individually sculpted working relationships with a range of stakeholders in order to meet the objectives of the project in a timely and cost effective manner. The ‘appropriateness’ of engagement varies considerably, and depends on a range of factors including criticality of the relationship to the success of the project, engagement that is culturally courteous and respectful, etc. The stakeholders range from include freehold and pastoral lease landholders, Aboriginal Landholders and Co-Management Boards, Native title organisations, DEWNR staff from the Permits unit and AWNRM Region, It is important to note that the engagement process for this project was crafted specifically for the duration and relatively minimal impact on the landscape of the survey work undertaken by the field team. Research projects need an engagement process specifically shaped to match the survey methodology duration and/or impact in the landscape.

Engagement for gaining permission to access land is the most critical area of engagement. Gaining access to Freehold land is generally the most straight forward, as the land manager is often the land owner and has the ‘authority’ to provide approval. Gaining access to sites on pastoral lease land is more complex as it requires not only approval by the lessee, but also involvement of Aboriginal heritage monitors to ensure the equipment is placed in culturally appropriate locations. Regardless of tenure, initial contact should be made as early as possible. Even with freehold land, in some instances the approval process can be time consuming. For example the manager living on the property may not be the owner and may need to forward the request to the landowner. In some cases access provisions such as site inductions and safety briefings may need to be negotiated.

As a rule of thumb initial contact should be made with the freehold and pastoral lease landholders at least a month prior to planned deployment of equipment. This provides sufficient time to be ‘courteous’. One month allows the landholder time to consider the request and ask questions, work through internal approval processes if necessary, consider any impacts on property management, and negotiate any access conditions. This also allows the project team the time to make adjustments to the deployment program to accommodate landholder preferences for timing of deployment on their

property. Any arrangements made during phone conversations should be summarised in a follow up email to the landholder as this ensures a written record of any decisions or arrangements is available for future reference by both parties if necessary. For the more remote properties the mobile phone network is patchy or non-existent. For landholders in these areas contact is limited to land line telephone and email. Telephone contact is often only possible outside of work hours before 7.30am and after 7.30pm.

Once permission to access land is granted the engagement process must continue. For both deployment and collection of equipment, ideally contact should be made 4-5 days prior to arrival at the property as a reminder for the landholder, and then again the day prior to arrival of the field team to confirm any arrangements. Wherever possible the team member involved in negotiating access should also be involved in deployment and collection of equipment on the property. Landholders appreciate the continuity of contact and this approach minimises the potential for misunderstandings between landholder and deployment team. Accurate notes of all communications with the landholder should be maintained to ensure any team member is able to communicate with the landholder regarding any previously discussed arrangements. On arrival at the property the field team should always call in to the homestead unless other arrangements have been made. Always ask if the landholder details about site location preferences and access issues. Invite the landholder to participate in the deployment and collection of equipment. In most cases they will decline, however it is important that the offer is made. Just prior to, or immediately after leaving the property contact should be made once again with the landholder, thanking them for allowing access and to let them know that the team has safely completed the installation/collection and left the property. After completion of survey work in the area official correspondence should be forwarded to participating landholders thanking them for their involvement and providing a summary of the project results.

Access to Aboriginal owned and/or managed land is significantly more complex. Most requests for access will need to go to a community council and /or land holding Council, or to a Co-management Board or Committee. These executive bodies may only meet infrequently and often have very full agendas. Notify the appropriate executive support person for these organisations as early as possible and wherever possible request to be present at the meeting to meet community members and demonstrate the equipment as the first steps towards building trust. It is recommended that contact be made at least 6 months prior to a scheduled deployment program. Once the formal gaining access to Aboriginal owned or Co-Managed land is completed the engagement transitions to the more informal process of engaging with Aboriginal communities and people commences involved in or supporting the actual field installation and collection of equipment. This is detailed below.

Engaging with Native Title organisations for negotiating the utilisation of heritage monitors on pastoral lease or for Co-Managed reserves can also be time consuming. For many Native Title bodies corporate the first point of contact is the legal entity representing these corporate bodies. A number of

Use existing local networks

The project team were able to utilise a number of existing government, landholder and NRM networks throughout the survey which proved to be of real benefit to the engagement process. Some of these benefits include:

- Streamlining the engagement process. The process for engaging with the plethora of stakeholders necessary to ensure access to land within SA and NSM is complex, particularly given the unprecedented scale of the project. By utilising networks developed and maintained by members of the project team both prior to, and during the term of the project, allowed the team to target the right people and organisations from the outset.

- Gaining access to several corporately pastoral properties that were reluctant to allow access for research. Access was granted as one of the field team was previously employed by the corporate pastoral company.
- Accessing information not readily available, such as cadastre information in NSW, and acquiring detailed pastoral lease maps for pastoral properties in SA.
- Utilising additional equipment and assets from other organisations. For example the field team were able to use the AW NRM land management office for accommodation at Oak Valley and use AW NRM camping equipment for Aboriginal heritage monitors during deployment trips on Maralinga Tjarutja lands and Mamungari CP.
- Introductions to stakeholders to accelerate process of building relationships and trust. For example the field team networks with AW NRM facilitated the process of attending the Mamungari CP Co-Management Board meeting on Mamungari CP in September 2014.

Approaches for successfully engaging with Aboriginal people and communities on Aboriginal Owned or Managed Land

Undertaking survey activities on Aboriginal owned and/or managed land necessitated the field team operate in a cross cultural setting, which added complexity and challenges. It also provided terrific reward to the field team from the experiences and enjoyment of working and travelling with traditional owners in their communities, and on their country.

Acquiring the skills, knowledge and confidence to operate effectively in a cross cultural setting requires time and experience. It was not possible for all project team members to be cross culturally proficient prior to commencing the engagement and field work, however some capability within the team was highly advantageous.

Fortunately Aboriginal people are generally very forgiving of non-Aboriginal people failing to understand local cultural norms and courtesies. To successfully engage with Aboriginal people and communities the field team found the following approaches to be very effective:

- Take time and care when communicating. Effectively communicating with Aboriginal people, located in remote Aboriginal communities can at times be problematic, particularly in relation to a project as technically complex as AusLAMP. For example English is a second language for many community members living at Oak Valley, Tjuntjuntjara and Yalata and conveying the technical aspects of the project to community members was difficult. This was further exacerbated by the fact that many of the older people that are nominated as heritage monitors had little or no formal schooling with limited English literacy and numeracy skills. It is important to avoid rapidly spoken and jargon filled sentences. Take the time to ensure any verbal communication is understood by politely reinforcing key elements and providing opportunity for questions to be asked and providing clarification. Use others with better language skills if necessary to communicate, particularly for critical conversations around field planning.
- Be patient. For many Aboriginal people, especially those located in remote communities there are a range of cultural differences that the field team must accommodate, and in particular a more relaxed approach to time management. On arrival in Aboriginal communities for fieldwork or meetings, it is likely that there may be other more pressing priorities in the community (though these may not be immediately obvious), which can impact on previously negotiated scheduling. Occasionally these community priorities may result in the need to postpone deployment trips. Invariably things are sorted in due course, however it is important to build flexibility in to deployment programs to accommodate competing priorities and unexpected issues that arise. It is important to keep in contact with the communities in the

weeks preceding the deployment to keep abreast of issues in the community that may impact on the project, and adapt and improvise the program accordingly. Many small remote Aboriginal Communities, such as Oak Valley, do not have mobile phone coverage, and few houses have land-line telephones so phone contact is predominantly via the community office telephone. Staff in the community office, store and essential services can sometimes help to provide some understanding of the issues in the community.

- Safe, steady and reassuring. On the first field trip incorporating Heritage Monitors it is important to understand that the Aboriginal people accompanying the field team are taking a leap of faith by being driven into the bush for several days by people they do not know, and whose driving and bush skills are likely to be inferior to their own. They will be quietly anxious and may be reluctant to engage in conversation. Do not try to push too hard and fast for conversation. Silence is ok. It is rude to continuously ask lots of questions. Take time to build trust and establish common ground and allow the conversation to grow gradually. Drive to the road conditions – slowly and carefully.
- Ask for and listen to advice. Be respectful of the advice, particularly about access to country such as road conditions, weather and cultural sensitivities prior to heading out to sites. Involve key Aboriginal people in the planning of field activities from the outset. Aboriginal traditional owners are extraordinarily knowledgeable about their country, but as a courtesy will not necessarily be forthcoming with their knowledge without being asked.
- Ngapartji ngapatji – we both learn and share together. Take time to allow Aboriginal Heritage monitors to talk about their country, visit the special places and teach some of their language. This creates an equal relationship whereby the project team learn about Aboriginal culture, country and language, and Aboriginal heritage monitors learn about the MT deployment process and objectives. Build time in to the field program to allow for these opportunities.
- Ask Aboriginal Heritage monitors to help undertake the installation work. For the most part the Heritage Monitors that accompanied the field team wanted to learn and be involved if their health allowed, but as a courtesy did not get involved unless encouraged to do so. Invite and encourage them to participate, take the time to teach the techniques, do not criticize, but rather recognise efforts and respectfully correct any poor installation/collection techniques.
- Ensure reasonable comfort and safety when camping out in remote locations. The Aboriginal people that accompanied the field team were not particularly fussy with food and were comfortable camping out in swags on country. The responsibility rests with the field team to ensure there is sufficient provisions and protection from the elements. Prior to heading out to remote locations it is important to check if there are any special dietary or medical requirements and ensure these are adequately organised, and ensure all participants have adequate bedding and clothing for the conditions. This is particularly important for the older people which may accompany the field team.
- Remember gender considerations. There can be cultural sensitivities around interactions between men and women, and also there may be areas in the country which have gender based access restrictions set according to traditional law. To manage around these sensitivities the best approach for the field team is to ask the Heritage Monitors if planned travel and camping arrangements are ok. Allow the Aboriginal people involved in the field camp to decide where they sit in vehicles, where they camp and lay their swags, and who can access which areas. Also the field team should consist of a male and female technicians to cater for gender specific interactions and site access issues.

Image removed

- Identify and utilise local champions. When engaging with remote Aboriginal communities to plan and prepare for field deployment of equipment it is advisable to try and identify a key contact in the community who has the cultural and community authority to be able to assist in organising local people, and is reasonably accessible for phone conversations with the field team leading up to arrival at the community for field deployment. It is important to recognise that these 'champions' are often in demand for a wide range of community management related issues which can be stressful and time consuming.
- Ensure prompt payment for use of local expertise. Perceived failure to provide the payment for services in a timely manner can be a major point of contention. On a number of occasions the heritage monitors required a cash advance for purchase of fuel and food to travel from their home to the rendezvous location to meet with the field team. For all employment of Aboriginal Heritage monitors by the AusLAMP campaigns the existing bodies corporate or community employment system were used to employ the heritage monitors, and then these entities invoiced the University of Adelaide for the employment costs. This provided a number of advantages including: utilising systems that were more nimble than the University of Adelaide particularly with regards to cash advances; reduction in administrative burden required set up new employment arrangements through the University, minimised risk to the University; and utilising systems that the Aboriginal heritage monitors were already familiar.

Field team experience and continuity

The AusLAMP project team responsible for delivering the three stages of AusLAMP in SA were broadly experienced in living and working in rural and remote communities, including living and working on pastoral stations, Aboriginal communities, and in seismic camps. Within its membership the team were also experienced in the management of National Parks and Reserves (particularly Co-Managed reserves) in outback South Australia, working with Natural Resources Management Boards and the Department for Environment and Natural Resources, and planning and implementing geophysical surveys in Central Australia. Furthermore the team were experienced in utilising the University of Adelaide procurement and administrative processes and procedures. This collective knowledge and skill set held by the project team proved to be highly advantageous not only for stakeholder engagement but for all aspects of delivering the AusLAMP project stages in South Australia.

In addition, the University of Adelaide was able to retain the services of the 3 core field team members for all three stages of the program. They who worked well together, and were respectful of each other and others involved in the project. They were committed to achieving the objectives of AusLAMP, ensuring the project was able to continuously draw from the accumulated skills and experience for the duration.

CONCLUSION

The principle objective of geophysical surveys and research over large geographical areas is to collect specified survey or research data for analysis and reporting. Ensuring 'effective engagement' is best described as a secondary objective, yet without effective engagement, particularly engagement with stakeholders responsible for granting permission to access land, the principle objective is unobtainable. Effective engagement is critical to ensure ongoing access to land for undertaking specified survey or research activities. All stages of the AusLAMP project delivered in South Australia so far have achieved the principle objective of acquiring a comprehensive and contiguous MT data set, and a major contributing factor in reaching this objective has been a highly successful stakeholder engagement process.

The project team members brought to the project a wealth of knowledge, experience and networks which was highly advantageous for ensuring effective engagement from the outset. The knowledge skills and networks were further developed through the many valuable lessons gained during delivery of the three project stages.

Stakeholder engagement for Stage 4 of AusLAMP within the Musgrave Province of South Australia commenced in January 2016 with field deployment expected to commence in July 2016. The lessons learned from the first three stages of AusLAMP in SA will be invaluable for the success of Stage 4, and for any future similar survey and research programs which require access to a large geographic areas across South Australia. It is important to note that the characteristics of engagement has to be sculpted to match the requirements specific to each project. Applying a copy-book set of procedures to different research projects will not work, however incorporating the stakeholder engagement processes documented above will maximise the likelihood of success.

REFERENCES

ANSIR - <http://ansir.org.au/index.php>

AuScope National MT Facility - <http://www.adelaide.edu.au/eei/ausscope>

AusLAMP - <http://www.ga.gov.au/about/what-we-do/projects/minerals/current/auslamp>

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Example of Correspondence from AARD re Heritage sites

Physical Id. DPC15D02266
File No. DPC15/0094

Emma Cordon
Project Manager - AusLAMP extension

Dear Emma

Thank you for your correspondence regarding the AusLAMP extension project, a geoscience research survey of the lower crust and upper mantle of the earth being part of AusLAMP, a broader project being rolled out nationally over the next 5 years.

I advise that the central archive, which includes the Register of Aboriginal Sites and Objects (the Register), administered by the Department of State Development-Aboriginal Affairs and Reconciliation (DSD-AAR), has entries for Aboriginal sites within this project.

These entries for Aboriginal sites are described as two archaeological sites and one cultural site. The enclosed map identifies the approximate site locations within 3 km of the relevant AusLAMP locations. It should be noted however that the site indicator does not reflect the actual area of the site, as this will vary from site to site, depending on the site information contained in the central archive. Please note there are many other sites within this project area however they are more than 3 km distance from AusLAMP locations. Please notify us if any of the AusLAMP locations are to change as we would need to conduct another search.

The applicant is advised that sites or objects may exist in the proposed development area, even though the Register does not identify them. All Aboriginal sites and objects are protected under the *Aboriginal Heritage Act 1988* (the Act), whether they are listed in the central archive or not. Land within 200 metres of a watercourse (for example the River Murray and its overflow areas) in particular, may contain Aboriginal sites and objects.

Pursuant to the Act, it is an offence to damage, disturb or interfere with any Aboriginal site or damage any Aboriginal object (registered or not) without the authority of the Minister for Aboriginal Affairs and Reconciliation (the Minister). If the planned activity is likely to damage, disturb or interfere with a site or object, authorisation of the activity must be first obtained from the Minister under Section 23 of the Act. Section 20 of the Act requires that any Aboriginal sites, objects or remains, discovered on the land, need to be reported to the Minister. Penalties apply for failure to comply with the Act.

It should be noted that this Aboriginal heritage advice has not addressed any relevant obligations pursuant to the *Native Title Act 1993*. Native title advice is provided by the Native Title Section of the Crown Solicitor's Office.

Aboriginal Affairs and Reconciliation
Level 7, 11 Waymouth Street | GPO Box 320 Adelaide SA 5001
Tel (+61) 08 8226 8900 | Fax (+61) 08 8226 8999 | www.statedevelopment.sa.gov.au | ABN 83 524 915 929

Please be aware in this area there are various Aboriginal groups/organisations/traditional owners that may have an interest, these may include:

DIERI NO 2 NATIVE TITLE MANAGEMENT COMMITTEE

Name: Stephen Kenny
Address: 345 King William Street ADELAIDE SA 5000

ADNYAMATHANHA TRADITIONAL LANDS ASSOCIATION

Chairperson: Michael Anderson
Postal Address:
Mobile: 0447808615
Email: rangelea@hotmail.com

NGADJURI NATION ABORIGINAL CORPORATION

Chairperson: Quenten Agius
Address: 46 Maitland Road POINT PEARCE SA 5573
Mobile: 0429 367 121
Email: Traditionalowners@adjahdura.com.au

MALYANGAPA PEOPLES

Address: South Australian Native Title Services Ltd
Level 4, 345 King William Street ADELAIDE SA 5000
Telephone: (08) 8110 2800 **Fax:** (08) 8110 2811
Email: info@nativetitlesa.org

WILYAKALI

Address: South Australian Native Title Services Ltd
Level 4, 345 King William Street ADELAIDE SA 5000
Telephone: (08) 8110 2800 **Fax:** (08) 8110 2811
Email: info@nativetitlesa.org

For further information please contact the Aboriginal Heritage Team on telephone (08) 8226 8900.

Yours sincerely

Perry Langeberg
SENIOR INFORMATION OFFICER (HERITAGE)
ABORIGINAL AFFAIRS & RECONCILIATION

8 May 2015

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Appendix 2: Information email to landholders

G'day David and Megan

Per our phone conversation Megan, please find attached some additional information on the research project.

Briefly, the project is being rolled out nationally, and Adelaide University will undertake most of the work in SA.

The research focuses on measuring the electrical and magnetic fields from 10km to 300km down through the earth. Geophysicists can use this information to gain a better understanding of the nature of the lower crust and upper mantle. The sites have been selected by dividing the continent up into a grid of 50km by 50km units, and measurements are required from within each unit. One site falls on Kokatha as shown on the attached map.

As indicated in the attached information sheet, the equipment used consists of a battery and portable hard drive inside a weather proof case the size of a small suitcase, a central sensor that requires a 40cm hole, and two sensors radiating out on 50m of cable. The equipment is passive - it emits no signals, chemicals or radiation, but simply measures the electrical and magnetic fields deep in the earth in that area. The equipment is left in place for around 3 weeks.

The location of the sites do not need to be precise - they can vary up to a few kilometres. The site locations are tentative and based on using existing roads and tracks. No off track driving is necessary. The final locations would be subject to discussion with, and approval by the landholder.

The field team consists of four people in two vehicles. On Kokotha I reckon we would need no more than half a day to install the site, and then about three weeks later we retrieve the equipment. The survey teams are fully equipped and self-sufficient. I expect the site would have no impact on your business. Whilst we encourage landholders/managers to accompany us while we install and retrieve the equipment, it is not essential. If landholders/managers do not have the time or the interest to be involved then that is fine.

Subject to your agreement we hope to be able to install the site on Kokotha on the 18th of November. However, we currently have 20 sites installed throughout properties between Stuarts Creek and Mobella and will be leaving on November 11 to collect them and reinstall them through a number of properties in the Gawler Ranges. You can appreciate that in working over such a vast area things can go wrong and the timing may change. I would keep in touch with you by Sat Phone if changes do occur, and definitely contact you few days prior to confirm our arrival at Kokotha.

I will ring in a couple of days to discuss further.

My mobile number is 0488 990 271 if you require any further information.

Thanks once again

Kind Regards

Geoff Axford

Project Officer

Adelaide University AusLAMP Deep Crustal Profile research project

Appendix 3: AusLAMP Information sheet

Deep-Crustal Research Survey - Information Sheet

The University of Adelaide is carrying out a deep-crustal research survey across South Australia from August 2014 until August 2015 as part of a national Geoscience Australia mapping project (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Station map across South Australia at a rough spacing of approximately 50 km.

The aim is to better understand the rocks and structures of the Earth's outermost layer (the crust and mantle), between 10 km and 300 km beneath the Earth's surface (see Figure 2). Data collected from the survey will contribute geoscience information to a national deep-crustal map of Australia.

Figure 2: The Earth is made of four distinct layers: crust, mantle, outer core and core (Ref: BBC GCSE Bitesize)

Why are we doing the survey?

There are still large parts of South Australia we know little about in terms of the Earth's processes that formed the rocks and rock structures deep beneath the ground. What geologists can physically see on

the earth's surface tells them very little about what is at depth, so they need to use other methods to build their understanding. An option with low environmental impact is the magnetotelluric geophysics (MTG) survey which we are using. This allows us to measure the natural variations in the Earth's magnetic and electric fields at the Earth's surface. Data collected will then be used to create a picture of what types of rocks and other geological formations are present in the lower crust and upper mantle of the Earth (10-300 km depth).

The outcome of this survey will be published in international scientific journals to improve our fundamental understanding of the Earth's geology.

What will it look like?

The survey equipment needs to be installed at approximately 50 km intervals across South Australia to effectively capture the required data. Recording data will occur at each site for around 3 weeks, after which we will collect the equipment and move it to a new site.

Each instrument consists of 1 logger box, 3 electrodes, and a series of cables. It is a very low impact device, and requires 4 small holes to be dug in order to install (see Figure 3). The equipment needs to be placed on the ground with cables to the electrodes going out 50 m in a north, and east direction. The three electrodes each need to be planted in a small hand dug hole, measuring approximately 5cm in diameter and 20 cm deep.

The magnetic sensor deployed about 10 m away from the grey box shown below.

One of the three holes for the electrodes (5cm x 20 cm). One electrode is situated next to the grey box and the other 2 about 50 m away to the north and east.

Figure 3: Pictures of the equipment and installation procedure.

Each hole is backfilled following the placement of the equipment and all holes will be backfilled following retrieval of the equipment. There will be no impact or damage to existing infrastructure, flora or fauna. The equipment will be deployed and retrieved by University of Adelaide staff using four-wheel drive vehicles.

We have a great deal of flexibility (a few kilometres from the planned locations) with where the equipment is located and prefer to use locations that have been previously disturbed, like road and rail reserves, and along fence lines. We always try to place equipment in a way that causes minimal interference and as such we are able to select sites that do not impact culturally sensitive areas.

In the meantime, if you require further information regarding the survey, please contact Graham Heinson on his mobile 0408 087 631 or by email graham.heinson@adelaide.edu.au.

Appendix 4: Example of MT site location map sent to landholders

Appendix 5: Example of follow up email to Landholders

G'day David

Just a short email to follow up from our phone conversation.

On behalf of the Adelaide University thank you for agreeing to have the equipment installed on Kokotha. Also, thanks for allowing me to obtain a copy of the Kokotha map from the Pastoral Program.

The deployment schedule has been updated. We commence on Tuesday November 11 collecting equipment already installed in the Kingoonya District. We are programmed to arrive at Kokotha on Sunday November 16. I will ring a day or so beforehand to confirm.

My mobile number is 0488 990 271 if you require any further information.

Thanks once again

Kind Regards

Geoff Axford

Project Officer

Adelaide University AusLAMP Deep Crustal Profile research project

Appendix 6: Example of information email to legal representative of Native Title groups

Dear Andrew

As discussed over the phone, the Adelaide University is undertaking a magneto-telluric research survey of the lower crust and upper mantle of the earth. The project is being rolled out nationally over the next 5 years, and Adelaide University will undertake all of the work in SA. The chief investigator for the project is Professor Graham Heinson, and project managed by Dr Stephan Thiel.

The research focuses on sensing the electrical and magnetic fields from approximately 1km to 300km down through the earth from surface measurements. The sites have been selected by dividing the continent up into a grid of 50km by 50km, and measurements are required from each grid point. The objective of the research is to map the deep Earth in order to understand the influence of past tectonic events on the shape of the continent as we see it today. The ultimate aim is to provide significant additional information about Australia's geodynamic framework. There still exist large parts of South Australia we know little about in terms of its tectonic history and the outcome of this survey will be published in international scientific journals to improve our fundamental understanding of Earth's processes.

The equipment used consists of a car battery and portable hard drive inside a weather proof recording case the size of a small suitcase, a central electrical sensor that requires a 40cm hole, and two electrical sensors, one 50m in one direction and another 50m at right angles to it. These are connected to the recording case by thin cable running over the ground. There is a third cable from the recording case that runs over the ground to a magnetometer buried in the ground about 400mm. The equipment is passive - it emits no signals or radiation, but simply measures the electrical and magnetic fields deep in the earth in that area. The equipment is left in place for approximately 3 weeks.

The site locations are tentative and based on using existing roads and tracks. The location of the sites do not need to be precise - they can vary up to a few kilometres to fit cultural sensitivities or station management needs. As indicated on the attached map, there are about 10 sites within the Gawler Ranges area, as indicated on the attached map.

We have provided details of proposed sites to AARD and they have made us aware of the Lake Gairdner site on the State Heritage Register. On advice from AARD we have been in contact with Andrew Starke in relation to how the project might work with traditional owners to access sites in the vicinity of Lake Gairdner.

Would it be possible for the Gawler Ranges Aboriginal Corporation to provide the University of Adelaide with two Cultural Heritage Monitors to assist the project team to locate and assess each of the proposed sites within the Gawler Ranges? We hope to schedule a field visit to the area to undertake this work in mid February and anticipate this would take about two and a half days.

Advice obtained by project managers is that the type of on ground activities undertaken by this project do not require authorisation or site clearance under provisions of the Native Title Act or the provisions of the Mining Act. However the project team would very much like to collaborate with Aboriginal traditional owners to ensure Aboriginal cultural heritage is appropriately considered in the location of sites.

The project management have indicated that the cultural heritage monitors would be paid at the similar rate as the project field officers equating to \$400/full day. All food and accommodation costs would also be covered by the project.

We would appreciate a response at your earliest convenience to allow time for planning the mid February field trip.

If you require further information please contact myself on 0488990271 or Pip Mawby on 08 83136794. We would be happy to meet with you to discuss the project in more detail.

Kind

Regards

Geoff Axford